

Species

COI gene of skipper

cytb gene of skipper

EF1-alpha gene of skipper

fbpa gene of skipper

ITS2 gene of skipper

COI gene of pine moth

Data types

- Image contribution
- DNA contribution

ITS1 gene of pine moth

ITS2 gene of pine moth

rbcl gene of plant

COI gene of bird

Contribution